

NOTES

are coordinated to the metal ion through both the sulphur atoms⁶. In the β -diketonato complexes the bands due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ were observed in the region $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively as expected, indicating the presence of coordinated carbonyl group of β -diketone⁷. Picolinic acid (Pyca) shows an absorption band between $1750\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was assigned⁸ to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ of the free $-\text{COOH}$ group. In the complexes under investigation, the band due to free $-\text{COOH}$ was found to be absent. Other bands due to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{COO}^-$ and pyridine ring were found to be present at 1610 and 1650 cm^{-1} as observed by Fowles *et al.*⁹. This suggests that picolinic acid is coordinated to the metal ion through oxygen and nitrogen atoms.

Electronic Spectra :

Though three transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ are expected for copper(II) complexes they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelop. Sacconi⁸ and Meek and Ehrhardt¹⁰ have observed that square planar complexes have complex broad band at relatively higher frequencies $\sim 16000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The regular tetrahedral complexes of copper(II) show no $d-d$ absorption bands in the region $10000\text{--}20000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.¹¹ The spectra of all the complexes now studied display a broad band around 16000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to a combination of the two transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ in D_{4h} symmetry¹². The position of this absorption band (16000 cm^{-1}) is in agreement with those generally observed for planar copper(II) complexes¹³⁻¹⁶. Thus, the compounds reported now are definitely four coordinated mixed chelate complexes of copper(II) with presumably square planar geometry.

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Determination of the Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Monoethanolamine Complexes with Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Y^{3+}

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IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-monoethanolamine with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-monoethanolamine was synthesized by method described in literature and repeatedly crystallized from ethanol to get an analytically pure compound with m.p. 153° .²

The experimental details are the same as described in the earlier communication³. The experimental technique of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here, that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium during titrations and by absence of any significant drift in pH, even after two hours. This was also corroborated by taking T.L.C. of a sample titration mixture, from time to time.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group, which takes part in the complex formation, and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of

dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A values against 'B' (pH meter readings). The curve extends over a range of $0.37 < \bar{n}_A < 1.83$ and is wavelike (Fig. 1). The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H

Fig. 1. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene monoethanolamine formation curve.

were determined from the half integral points at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. These values were also corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B and $\log(2 - \bar{n}_A/\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs B. Formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria were obtained from the plots of \bar{n} vs pL (Fig. 2). From these, the values of the stability constants $\log K_1$ were calculated at $\bar{n} = 0.5$. These values were further corroborated by the plot of $\log(\bar{n}/1 - \bar{n})$ vs pL.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene monoethanolamine formation curves.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stabilities of trivalent metal chelates is $Pr^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Gd^{3+}$.

If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E = Z^2/2r(1 - \frac{1}{D})$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge 'Z' and

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cations	$t = 25^\circ$					
	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Y^{3+}
$\log K_1$	11.05	14.10	10.90	11.12	11.90	11.06
$\log K_2$	8.45	—	—	—	—	—

radius 'r' in a medium of dielectric constant 'D'. Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the log K values should increase linearly with Z^2/r .

The plots of log K against Z^2/r tend to diverge widely as regards a linear relationship. The results are similar to those reported by Khanolkar and Ingle⁴ who explain these deviations on the basis that the assumption regarding the ionic character of the metal-ligand bond may not be valid. The deviations may be accounted for by the increased covalent nature of the bonding in the rare earth complexes, where the ligands have N and O atoms as the donor set.

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Complexes of Mono- and Di-tertiaryphosphine Sulphides or Selenides with Zinc(II) and Mercury(II)

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VERY few complexes of zinc(II) with mono- and di-tertiaryphosphine sulphides are known¹⁻³. There is no adduct of a corresponding phosphine selenide with any zinc(II) salt. However, in contrast to